

ABSTRACT

A key feature of advanced motion processing in the primate dorsal stream is the existence of pattern cells – specialized cortical neurons that integrate local motion signals into pattern-invariant representations of global direction. Pattern cells have also been reported in rodent visual cortex, but it is unknown whether the tuning of these neurons results from truly integrative, nonlinear mechanisms or trivially arises from linear receptive fields (RFs) with a peculiar geometry. Here we show that pattern cells in rat visual cortical areas V1 and LM process motion direction in a way that cannot be explained by the linear spatiotemporal structure of their RFs. Instead, their tuning properties are consistent with and well explained by those of units in a state-of-the-art neural network model of the dorsal stream. This suggests that similar cortical processes underlay motion representation in primates and rodents. The latter could thus serve as powerful model systems to unravel the underlying circuit-level mechanisms.

USAGE NOTES

Source data file for the article authored by Matteucci et al. on pattern-invariant motion processing in the rat visual cortex.

This data file provides the data set processed in the article “Truly pattern: nonlinear integration of motion signals is required to account for the responses of pattern cells in rat visual cortex” by Giulio Matteucci et al. A detailed description of the file is provided in the companion “Readme_for_Matteucci_et_al_source_data.pdf” file.

FILES

- Matteucci_et_al_source_data.zip
- Readme_for_Matteucci_et_al_source_data.pdf

REFERENCES

This dataset is supplement to doi: <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adh4690>

KEYWORDS

rat, visual cortex, pattern cells, component cells, global motion, plaid patterns